

Appendix A – The survey instrument

Consent: First page will include a summary of the project, link to the protocol, and a request to consent to participate and use the collected data in a publicly available report/publication (tick box).

Demographic questions:

1. Are you currently contributing to, or have you previously contributed to, evidence syntheses on **environmental health and/or toxicology topics**? (Evidence syntheses are defined here as systematic reviews, systematic maps, scoping reviews, or other types of evidence reviews or syntheses)
 - a. Yes
 - b. No
2. In which **disciplines other than environmental health and/or toxicology**, are you currently contributing to, or have you previously contributed to, evidence syntheses? (multiple selections allowed)
 - a. Health (including allied health)
 - b. Business or management
 - c. Crime, justice, or policing
 - d. Education
 - e. Methodology (for any field/discipline)
 - f. Social care or social welfare
 - g. None
 - h. Others [text box to write in]
3. What **role** do you currently play, or have you previously played, in evidence syntheses?: (multiple selections allowed)
 - a. Content expert (e.g., clinician on clinical topics, environmental scientist on environmental topics, etc.)
 - b. Search expert (e.g., librarian, informationist, information specialist, search specialist, etc.)
 - c. Methodologist (knowledge of how to conduct evidence syntheses – including evidence synthesis methodology, statistics/quantitative synthesis, qualitative synthesis)
 - d. Active participation in the selection, evaluation, analysis, or interpretation of evidence (e.g., screening, data extraction, quality or bias assessment, synthesis of findings, writeup)
 - e. Other [write in]
4. How many **years of experience** in contributing to evidence **syntheses (on any topics/disciplines)** do you have?
 - a. Drop down box with ranges; respondent will select one of: 0, 1-2, 3-5, 6-10, 11-15, 16-20, 21-25, 26-30, >30

5. How many **years of experience** in contributing to **evidence syntheses (on EHT topics specifically)** do you have?
 - a. Drop down box with ranges; respondent will select one of: 0, 1-2, 3-5, 6-10, 11-15, 16-20, 21-25, 26-30, >30
6. How many **evidence syntheses** on EHT topics have you contributed to?
 - a. Drop down box with ranges; respondent will select one of: 0, 1-2, 3-5, 6-10, 11-15, 16-20, 21-25, 26-30, >30
7. For **whom/what type of organisation do you currently contribute to, or have previously contributed to, evidence syntheses on EHT topics.** (This may or may not be your employer – e.g. if a government dept. commissions you/your employer to conduct evidence syntheses, select Government.)? (multiple selections allowed)
 - a. Academia (university, college, etc.)
 - b. Government
 - c. Non-government organisation
 - d. Industry
 - e. Consultancy
 - f. Other [free text]
8. Currently/most recently, what **type of employer** are you mainly working for? (if multiple employers - the one you spend most of your working time working for)
 - a. Academia (university, college, etc.)
 - b. Government
 - c. Non-government organisation
 - d. Industry
 - e. Consultancy
 - f. Other [free text]
9. Where is your main **employer** (the one you spend most time working for, e.g. if you have several employers) **located**?
 - a. [drop down list of countries]

Content questions

1. What types of evidence/sources do you **consider to be 'grey literature'** when conducting evidence syntheses on EHT topics?
 - a. Books or book chapters
 - b. Data (e.g., database, data sets, safety data/MSDS, data analyses)
 - c. Educational/training materials (e.g., lectures, presentations, curricula, etc.)
 - d. Encyclopaedias (online or hardcopy)
 - e. Guidelines (e.g., clinical, practice, etc.)
 - f. Handbooks
 - g. Legal documentation (statutes/legislation/patents/standards)
 - h. Manuals
 - i. Meeting or conference publications (e.g., abstracts, posters, proceedings, etc.)
 - j. Newsletters/newspapers
 - k. Other brief publications, e.g., brochures, bulletins, leaflets, etc.
 - l. Project documentation

- m. Registers (e.g., clinical, study registries, research registers)
 - n. Reports - government (e.g., agency, ministry) at any level (federal, state, local), including policy documents
 - o. Reports - industry
 - p. Reports - other (e.g., green papers, technical reports, feasibility reports, etc.)
 - q. Risk analyses
 - r. Social media
 - s. Technical documentation
 - t. Theses and dissertations
 - u. Transcripts
 - v. Unpublished articles (e.g., preprints)
 - w. Visual sources (e.g., videos, photographs, maps)
 - x. Other [free text/write-in]
2. Which types of evidence/sources have you **included** in your EHT evidence syntheses?
- a. Books or book chapters
 - b. Data (e.g., database, data sets, safety data/MSDS, data analyses)
 - c. Educational/training materials (e.g., lectures, presentations, curricula, etc.)
 - d. Encyclopaedias (online or hardcopy)
 - e. Guidelines (e.g., clinical, practice, etc.)
 - f. Handbooks
 - g. Legal documentation (statutes/legislation/patents/standards)
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 - t. Theses and dissertations
 - u. Transcripts
 - v. Unpublished articles (e.g., preprints)
 - w. Visual sources (e.g., videos, photographs, maps)
 - x. Other [free text/write-in]
3. **Why do you include** grey literature in your EHT evidence syntheses?
- a. free text box to write in the answer
4. If you conduct your EHT evidence syntheses in English, do you **search for 'grey literature' sources in languages other than English?**

- a. Yes
 - b. No
 - c. Not applicable (I conduct my EHT evidence syntheses in a language other than English)
5. What **sources do you search** to identify grey literature for inclusion in your evidence syntheses on EHT topics? Please indicate (if possible) whether those sources are free to access or require payment.
- a. Not applicable (I am not involved in searching)
 - b. Free text box to write in
6. Does your organisation have a **standardised protocol or approach for searching** for grey literature on EHT topics?
- a. Yes
 - b. No
 - c. Not sure
 - d. Not applicable
7. If you include grey literature in your EHT evidence syntheses, **how do you treat grey literature evidence?**
- a. Not applicable (I don't include grey literature in my EHT syntheses)
 - b. On par with published literature (peer reviewed articles)
 - c. Differently than published literature (peer reviewed articles)
8. **If you treat grey literature differently** than you treat published literature (peer reviewed articles) in your EHT evidence syntheses, **what is the difference?**
- a. Not applicable (I treat grey literature on par with published literature)
 - b. Report the published (peer reviewed articles) and grey literature in separate sections
 - c. Use a different approach to risk of bias/quality assessment
 - d. Conduct sensitivity analyses including and excluding the findings from grey literature
 - e. Other [free text box]
9. Any other comments (e.g., important topics or issues you come across when it comes to grey literature in evidence synthesis)
- a. [free text box]

Thank you very much for sharing your expertise and experiences with us.